

Annotated Résumé for Researchers (R4R) Narrative CV Template

This annotated CV template aims to illustrate the commonalities of [Résumé for Researchers](#) (R4R)-like CVs as used by some members of the [Joint Funders Group](#). This example was informed by the [R4R-like narrative CV template synthesis](#) undertaken in January 2022.

Figure 1: [Résumé for Researchers](#) page 1

Résumé for Researchers

Below is the suggested structure for the Résumé for Researchers tool.

Personal details

Provide your personal details, your education, key qualifications and relevant positions you have held.

All funders ask for applicants' personal details. The majority do not include this specific ask as a section within the CV template as these details are collected elsewhere within the application

Figure 2: [Résumé for Researchers](#) page 2

All ask for applicants' contribution to the generation of knowledge

Module 1 – How have you contributed to the generation of knowledge?

This module can be used to explain how you have contributed to the generation of new ideas and hypotheses and which key skills you have used to develop ideas and test hypotheses. It can be used to highlight how you have communicated on your ideas and research results, both written and verbally, the funding you have won and any awards that you have received. It can include a small selection of outputs, with a description of why they are of particular relevance and why they are considered in the context of knowledge generation. Outputs can include open data sets, software, publications, commercial, entrepreneurial or industrial products, clinical practice developments, educational products, policy publications, evidence synthesis pieces and conference publications that you have generated. Where outputs have a DOI please only include this.

Module 2 – How have you contributed to the development of individuals?

This module can be used to highlight expertise you provided which was critical to the success of a team or team members including project management, collaborative contributions, and team support. It can include your teaching activities, workshops or summer schools in which you were involved (for undergrads, grads and post-grads as well as junior colleagues), and the supervision of students and colleagues. It can be used to mention mentoring of members in your field and support you provided to the advancement of colleagues, be it junior or senior. It can be used to highlight the establishment of collaborations, from institutional (maybe interdisciplinary) to international. It can be used to describe where you exerted strategic leadership, how you shaped the direction of a team, organisation, company or institution.

All ask applicants to demonstrate how they have contributed to the development of individuals, or questions aligned to this

Figure 3: [Résumé for Researchers](#) page 3

All ask for applicants' contribution to the wider research community, or questions aligned to this

Module 3 – How have you contributed to the wider research community?

This module can include various activities you have engaged in to progress the research community. It can be used to mention commitments including editing, reviewing, refereeing, committee work and your contributions to the evaluation of researchers and research projects. It can be used to mention the organisation of events that have benefited your research community. It can highlight contributions to increasing research integrity, and improving research culture (gender equality, diversity, mobility of researchers, reward and recognition of researchers' various activities). It can be used to mention appointments to positions of responsibility such as committee membership and corporate roles within your department, institution or organisation, and recognition by invitation within your sector.

Module 4 – How have you contributed to broader society?

This module can include examples of societal engagement and knowledge exchange. It can include engagement with industry and the private sector. It can be used to mention engagement with the public sector, clients and the broader public. It can be used to highlight positive stakeholder feedback, inclusion of patients in processes and clinical trials, and other impacts across research, policy, practice and business. It can be used to mention efforts to collaborate with particular societal or patient groups. It can be used to highlight efforts to advise policy-makers at local, national or international level and provide information through the press and on social media.

Many ask for applicants to outline contribution to broader society

Figure 4: [Résumé for Researchers](#) page 4

Personal statement

Some ask for applicants' personal statement/declaration

Provide a personal statement that reflects on your overarching goals and motivation for the activities in which you have been involved.

Additions

Mention career breaks, secondments, volunteering, part-time work and other relevant experience (including in time spent in different sectors) that might have affected your progression as a researcher.

Many provide applicants' space to provide additional information. Some are explicit about what this might include e.g. career breaks

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Version Control

<u>Version Number</u>	<u>Status</u>	<u>Revision Date</u>	<u>Author(s)</u>	<u>Summary of Changes</u>
1.0	Complete	March 2022	Joint Funders Group	New resource created